

THE INFLUENCE OF WATERING AND FERTILIZING RATES ON THE YIELD OF COTTON VARIETY “BESH KHAHRAMON”

Kurbanova G.A.

Candidate of agricultural sciences of Fine Staple Cotton Research Institute

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Abstract. *It is known to everybody that our respected President Sh.M. Mirziyoev is aimed at deepening economic reforms in the agricultural sector of the republic, fully satisfying the needs of the population for food and other agricultural products and raw materials for industry, bringing our country to the level of developed countries in the agricultural sector, it is necessary to grow high-quality products.*

Keywords: *soil and infertile soil, irrigation of fine-fiber cotton varieties.*

It is known to everybody that our respected President Sh.M. Mirziyoev is aimed at deepening economic reforms in the agricultural sector of the republic, fully satisfying the needs of the population for food and other agricultural products and raw materials for industry, bringing our country to the level of developed countries in the agricultural sector, it is necessary to grow high-quality products. Therefore, rational management of agricultural production requires the use of effective methods and technologies for the use of land and water resources, taking into account the soil and climatic conditions of each region.

According to V.T. Lev, A.E. Avliyokulov [1], they write that for newly irrigated lands of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis with a deep layer of soil and infertile soil, irrigation of fine-fiber cotton varieties using the 1-5-1 system gave good results. At the same time, the authors consider it desirable to maintain soil moisture at the level of 70-70-(75)-70% relative to the BSN.

It is important that in experiments conducted by V.T. Lev, P. Khasanov [2] in Surkhandarya region with low-saline, medium-sandy, meadow-desert soils, the fine-fiber cotton variety 5904-I had 1.1 thousand m³ of about 70% pre-water moisture before flowering relative to CHDNS/ha, at the rate of 75% during the flowering-fruiting period, at the rate of 1.2 thousand m³/ha during the ripening period and at 70% humidity at the rate of 1.1 thousand m³/ha. according to the water norm (40-42 c/ha). It was noted that the volume of seasonal irrigation was 10.5 thousand m³/ha.

According to the results of experiments Avliyokulov A.E. [3], the highest cotton yield (35-38 t/ha) for fine-fiber cotton varieties 5904-I and T-7 on the infertile soils of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis is 6-7 times higher. during the irrigation period, the irrigation system is 1-4-1 or 1-5-1 and seasonal water standards are obtained from options 8237-9411 m³/ha. As a result of research, it was found effective to irrigate fine-fiber cotton at a rate of 800-900 m³/ha before flowering, 190-1300 m³/ha during the flowering-harvesting period and 900 m³/ha during the ripening period.

Yuldashev G. et al. [4] wrote that the seasonal irrigation norm in the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions is 7500 to obtain early and high yields of fine-fiber cotton varieties C-6029 and C-6030.

m³/ha, humidity 70-70-60% in meadow soils of the Bukhara region. An acceptable figure is about 7000 m³/ha.

Avliyokulov N.E. [5] in studies conducted in the Surkhan-Sherabad desert, on irrigated barren and meadow-desert soils (1.5-2 m), the cotton variety Termiz-14 was planted 6-7 times in 1-3-2.1 -4- 2 irrigation systems, pre-irrigation soil moisture should be of the order of 70-75-65% compared to the PDNS, irrigation rates should be 700-900 m³/ha before cotton flowering and 800-900 m³/ha during. When ripe, the seasonal amount of water should be 5400-6500 m³/ha.

According to Kh. Zakirov [6], according to the results of experiments carried out to develop the optimal irrigation regime for fine-fiber cotton variety T-7 on the meadow-desert soils of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, the T. -7 variety should be watered in the order of 70-70-60% compared with ChDNS and standard fertilizer NPK 220; 220; At a rate of 110 c/ha, the growth, development and productivity of cotton were high.

According to the results of experiments conducted by M. Tojiev and others [7] in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, to obtain a high yield of medium-fiber cotton varieties, they are placed with a thickness of 90-90 thousand bushels/ha, the amount of fertilizer NPK 180; 130; 90 kg/ha, it is advisable to water the soil before planting, and water the plants 6 times during the growing season.

According to M. Tojiev and others [8], in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, the varieties Akkurgan-2, Bukhoro-102, S-2 and Denov were irrigated at a pre-irrigation humidity of 70-70-60% according to the mineral fertilizer system 1-3- 2 NPK 180; 130; 90 and 220; 160; It is better to use 110 c/ha, and leave the planting thickness at 80-90 thousand bushes/ha.

In 2010-2011, research was carried out on the field of the Surkhan farm in the Jarkurgan region. To solve the issues of the scientific work program, field experiments were carried out on a single system and two variants of the new promising variety Besh Herod Goza, taking into account the limited field moisture capacity (LCMC) before irrigation of 60-65-60%. , 70-70-65%, mineral fertilizers (NPK) two rates 200; 140; 100 and 250; 125 kg/ha, seedling thickness 80-100 thousand/ha. To determine the conditions and norms for watering cotton varieties, soil layers of 0-70 cm were taken into account before flowering and ripening and layers of 0-100 cm during flowering and harvesting.

Scientific research was carried out in laboratory, field and industrial experiments in accordance with the methodological guidelines developed at UzPITI.

In the experiment, the options were placed in 4 rows in one row. The area of the options is 720 sq.m. m (8 rows, of which the middle 4 rows are calculated, the two protective rows following them, the length of the fence is 100 m, the seeds are planted according to the 90x15x1-2 system.

Five types of heroes.

The origin of the variety “Besh khahramon” (*G. hirsutum* .L) was obtained by crossing the varieties L-517 and AN-415, obtained by crossing within the species (*G. hirsutum* .L) in the laboratory of the city of embryogenetics of the Institute of Genetics and Experimental Plant Biology RFA T. Creator I. Mukhiddinov and others.

Morphobiological characteristics of the variety: Plant height 110-120 cm, number of sympadia branches 15-17, degree of branching 1.0-1.5 type, general appearance pyramidal, body green, strong. does not bend, green, has anthocyanin spots, monopadia 1-2 horned. The first harvest horn (syllable pitch) appears at the 5th-6th joint.

Economic characteristics of the variety. The growing season is 98-105 days in the south, 109-111 days in Tashkent. This variety belongs to the tezpishar group. Weight of 1000 seeds is 118-120 g. Medium size cup, 5.5-6.5 g. It looks like an egg. 4-5 cups, cotton is not fluffy.

Technological indicators: fiber yield 40-42%, microns 4.2-4.4, fiber length 33.8-35.2 mm, specific tensile strength gf/tex 29.2-31.1, white fiber belongs to IV industrial type. Productivity 41.0-42.0 c/ha per hectare.

In 2010-2011, during the experiment, 8 variants of the NPK received plowing along with sowing, while cotton yielded 3-4 cymes,

applied at the beginning of the flowering period.

The soil of the experimental field is grey-earth, the depth of water penetration exceeds 3 m. Water permeability of the soil of the experimental field at the beginning of the operation period (2010-2011). 925-968 m³/ha for a six-hour observation. was equal

At the end of the implementation period, a significant decrease was observed - 540-600 m³/ha due to soil compaction under the influence of irrigation and inter-row cultivation.

The maximum field moisture capacity (MFMC) at the beginning of the operational period (2010-2011) was 21.6-21.1%, in the 0-70 cm layer - 21.7-22.1%. Soil volumetric weight 0-70; In layers 0-100 cm in early spring it was 1.33-1.35 g/cm, in late autumn - 1.35-1.39 g/cm.

An important task is to determine the optimal soil moisture limit before irrigation for the cotton variety under study.

The difference in the available moisture content of the field soil under study before irrigation did not exceed 0.5-1.5% compared to the ChDNS, when it was maintained in the amount specified by the program.

Watering in experiment 1-2-1; Conducted in systems 1-3-2. The rate of working water before flowering is 845 m³/ha (60-65-60%), 875 m³/ha (70-70-65%); 1186 m³/ha (60-65-60%) during flowering and harvesting; 1235 m³/ha (70-70-65%)); during the ripening period, humidity is 955 m³/ha; 887 m³/ha, seasonal irrigation norms 60-65-60%; 5360 m³/ha by humidity; At 70-70-65% it amounted to 6355 m³/ha.

Duration of watering before flowering - 21.00 hours, min until 23.10; flowering-harvest; from 29.05 to 45.40 h.m.; and during the ripening period it was equal to 22.20 - 40.10 hours, thousand. According to the data of two-year (2010-2011) sown varieties according to the options, the pre-harvest thickness of seedlings of the new Beshkhahramon variety was provided from 79-82 to 98-102.5 thousand bushels.

Phenological observations were carried out on the growth, development and yield of five hero varieties. According to the options, at a higher level of soil moisture before watering, the growth of the main stem accelerated, and the difference between the options was: significant in terms of the number of crop branches, nodes (flowers, pods). The height of the main stem (September 3-5) was as follows, depending on the variety tested in the experiment. It was noted that the height of the cotton plant of this variety reached 90-111 cm. The main goal of studying water standards, nutrition and irrigation procedures is to create conditions for the appearance of more buds, bolls, flowers and bolls and abundant high-quality buds in cultivated varieties of cotton with a moisture content of 65-70-65%; Norms 60-65-60% NPK 250; 175; 125; kg/ha during the research was observed with irrigation 4-6 times, in systems 1-2-1, 1-3-2, in these options there were more pods, and there were 10.5-13.0 pieces. assembled at the Intervariant plant. Soil moisture before watering 70-70-65% and during work 4-6 times 1-2-1; Therefore, 1-3-2 systems are watered, until flowering 875 m³/ha; Abundant and high-quality yields were obtained during the flowering and harvesting period of 1235 m³/ha and 887 m³/ha during the ripening period, and seasonal irrigation norms amounted to 6355 m³/ha. 38.7-42.9 t/ha harvested.

In short, soil moisture in irrigated options is 60-65-60%; 845 m³/ha before flowering, 1186 m³/ha during flowering, 955 m³/ha during ripening, seasonal irrigation rate 5360 m³/ha, yield 0.9-4.3 t/ha, top quality harvest according to NPK standards; 250 175 125 c/ha were grown. The growth, development and yield of cotton decreased (35.3-35.5 c/ha) in the order of a slight decrease in soil moisture (60-65-60%), especially in options with lower NPK rates 200140100 kg/ha (agricultural).

**The influence of watering and fertilizing rates on the yield of cotton
 variety "Besh khahramon"**

№	Options			Seedling thickness, thousand/bush	Irrigation volume, duration m ³ /ha				Cotton yield c/ha			
	Varieties	Fertilizer rates kg/ha	Irrigation system, NPV%		Before flowering period	Flowering and harvesting period	Ripe period	Seasonal irrigation period	cotton harvest in 2010, c/ha	cotton harvest in 2011, c/ha	two annual medium cotton Productivity, c/ha.	1c harvest went to pick it up water consumption, m ³ /ha
1.	DESH KHAHRAMON	200,140,100	60-65-60	80	845	1186	955	5360	35.0	35.6	35.3	152
2.		250,175,125	60-65-60	80	845	1186	955	5360	37.0	37.3	37.1	144
3.		200,140,100	70-70-65	80	875	1235	887	6355	39.0	38.5	38.7	164
4.		250,175,125	70-70-65	80	875	1235	887	6355	42.0	42.1	42.0	150
5.		200,140,100	60-65-60	100	845	1186	955	5360	36.5	34.5	35.5	150
6.		250,175,125	60-65-60	100	845	1186	955	5360	38.1	36.4	37.2	144
7.		200,140,100	70-70-65	100	875	1235	887	6355	40.1	39.2	39.6	160
8.		250,175,125	70-70-65	100	875	1235	887	6355	43.0	42.8	42.9	148

(Control type - Namangan-77)

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